

Potential Antimycobacterial Agents: Part III. Condensation Products of Diphenylamine-2-Carboxylic acid Hydrazides with Aldehydes and Ketones and Their Evaluation as Antibacterials

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Manuscript received 20 February 1975; revised 2 June 1975; accepted 24 June 1975.

Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides, synthesised by the hydrazinolysis of methyl diphenylamine-2-carboxylates have been condensed with aromatic aldehydes, ketones and α -isonitrosopropiophenone. Some of the compounds possessed 'significant' antibacterial activity.

RECENTLY we have reported the synthesis of a large number of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazines^{1,2}. Several such compounds are known to have significant antibacterial³ and antimycobacterial⁴ properties. This work has now been extended. The present communication deals with the synthesis of a variety of condensation products (II, III and IV) of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides (I) with aryl aldehydes, ketones and α -isonitrosopropiophenone.

Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid obtained from 2-chloro benzoic acid and aromatic amine was esterified. The methyl ester was then treated with 95% hydrazine hydrate^{1,2} to furnish diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides (I). I were condensed with various carbonyl compounds. (II), (III) and (IV) thus obtained were evaluated for their antimicrobial

properties. A majority of the compounds listed in Table I were found to exhibit significant activity, a number of them inhibiting specially the growth of *S. aureus*, when compared to those reported earlier³. However, the inhibitory effects were less marked for compounds listed in Tables 2 and 3. Only a few of these possessed antibacterial property.

Biological data

The method developed by Varma and Nobels⁵ was employed for determining the antibacterial spectrum of all the compounds. The test organisms included *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus magaterium*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*. Sterile filter paper discs (5 mm diameter), saturated with the test compounds (10 mg/ml in acetone) were placed on the plated nutrient agar (1.5% agar, 0.5% NaCl,

TABLE 1

S.N.	R	R'	m.p. °c	Molecular formula	% Analysis		Antibacterial activity against*			
					Calcd.	Found	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>B.maga- terium</i>	<i>S.typhi</i>	<i>S.aureus</i>
1.	2-OCH ₃	4-NO ₂	177-78	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	C 64.62 H 4.61 N 14.35	64.23 4.50 14.40	+	-	-	-
2.	2-OCH ₃	4-Br	210	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ BrN ₃ O ₂	C 59.42 H 4.24 N 9.90	59.40 4.20 10.05	-	-	-	-
3.	2-OCH ₃	4-Cl	189	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂	C 66.40 H 4.63 N 11.07	66.00 5.10 11.00	+	-	-	-
4.	2-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	180	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃	C 70.41 H 7.05 N 11.20	70.81 7.05 11.00	+	+	+	+
5.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	4-NO ₂	126	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄	C 65.34 H 4.95 N 13.83	65.00 4.63 13.51	-	-	-	-
6.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	4-Br	162	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ BrN ₃ O ₂	C 60.27 H 4.56 N 9.78	60.34 4.50 10.14	-	-	++	+
7.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	4-Cl	154	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₂	C 67.09 H 5.08 N 10.67	67.15 5.03 10.50	-	-	-	-
8.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	4-OCH ₃	153	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃	C 70.95 H 5.91 N 10.79	71.08 5.82 10.70	+	-	+	+
9.	3-Cl	4-NO ₂	165	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃	C 60.84 H 3.80 N 14.19	61.24 3.50 14.20	-	-	-	+
10.	3-Cl	4-Br	192-3	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ BrClN ₃ O	C 56.00 H 3.50 N 9.80	55.84 3.61 9.51	+	++	++	-
11.	3-Cl	4-Cl	191	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O	C 62.50 H 3.90 N 10.93	62.41 4.09 10.93	-	-	-	+
12.	3-Cl	4-OCH ₃	187-88	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂	C 66.40 H 4.74 N 11.33	66.05 4.75 11.00	-	-	+	+
13.	4-Br	4-NO ₂	220	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₃	C 54.66 H 3.41 N 12.52	55.10 3.40 12.50	+	-	-	+
14.	4-Br	4-Br	198-99	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Br ₂ N ₃ O	C 50.74 H 3.17 N 8.88	50.74 3.15 9.00	++	+	+	+
15.	4-Br	4-Cl	195	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ BrClN ₃ O	C 56.00 H 3.50 N 9.80	56.41 3.47 10.05	+	+	+	+
16.	4-Br	4-OCH ₃	179	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ BrN ₃ O ₂	C 59.43 H 4.24 N 9.90	59.43 4.30 10.00	-	-	-	-

* - = No inhibition
 + = Zone size 6-8 mm
 ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm
 +++ = Zone size greater than 10 mm.

TABLE 2

S.N.	R	R	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	% Analysis		Antibacterial activity against*			
					Calcd.	Found	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>B.maga- terium</i>	<i>S.typhi</i>	<i>S.aureus</i>
17.	H	CH ₃	179	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	C 76.42 H 5.77 N 12.76	76.34 6.04 12.50	-	-	-	-
18.	2-CH ₃	CH ₃	172	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O	C 76.96 H 6.12 N 12.58	76.45 6.10 12.50	-	-	-	-
19.	3-CH ₃	CH ₃	165	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O	C 76.96 H 6.12 N 12.58	76.45 6.00 12.58	-	-	-	-
20.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	166	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O	C 76.97 H 6.12 N 12.58	77.21 5.87 13.00	-	-	+	-
21.	3-Cl	CH ₃	134	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O	C 67.75 H 4.95 N 11.55	68.13 5.31 11.22	+	+++	-	+
22.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	157	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	C 73.99 H 6.16 N 11.26	74.40 6.15 11.25	-	-	-	-
23.	2-OCH ₃	CH ₃	151	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	C 74.94 H 5.88 N 11.76	74.05 6.01 11.84	-	+	-	+
24.	H	C ₂ H ₅	170	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O	C 76.96 H 6.12 N 12.58	76.51 6.00 13.00	+	-	-	-
25.	2-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	152	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O	C 76.76 H 6.44 N 10.01	76.41 6.44 10.40	-	-	+	+
26.	3-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	157	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O	C 76.76 H 6.44 N 10.01	77.00 6.05 10.00	+	-	-	-
27.	4-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	170	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O	C 76.76 H 6.44 N 10.01	76.45 6.44 9.76	-	-	+	+
28.	3-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	150	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	C 69.93 H 5.29 N 11.13	69.90 5.30 11.43	+	+++	+	++
29.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	121	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	C 74.42 H 6.45 N 10.43	74.40 6.40 11.43	-	-	-	-
30.	2-OCH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	137	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	C 73.99 H 6.16 N 11.26	74.00 6.15 11.00	-	-	-	-

* - = No inhibition
 + = Zone size 6-8 mm
 ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm
 +++ = Zone size greater than 10 mm.

TABLE 3

S.N.	R	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	% Analysis		Antibacterial activity against*				
				Calcd.	Found	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>B.maga-</i> <i>terium</i>	<i>S.typhi</i>	<i>S.aureus</i>	
31.	H	193	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	C	70.98	71.00	+	+	+	+
				H	3.38	3.00				
				N	15.05	15.40				
32.	2-CH ₃	215	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	C	71.14	72.01	-	-	+	++
				H	5.67	6.04				
				N	14.43	14.90				
33.	3-CH ₃	201	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	C	71.14	71.00	-	-	-	-
				H	5.57	5.50				
				N	14.43	14.40				
34.	4-CH ₃	205	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	C	71.14	71.14	-	-	-	-
				H	5.67	6.00				
				N	14.43	14.40				
35.	3-Cl	196	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₂	C	64.95	64.90	-	+	+	-
				H	4.66	4.60				
				N	13.78	14.00				
36.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	187	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃	C	69.23	69.23	-	-	-	-
				H	8.81	8.80				
				N	13.46	13.50				
37.	2-OCH ₃	211	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₃	C	68.66	69.04	+	-	-	-
				H	5.47	5.45				
				N	13.93	14.20				
38.	4-Br	217	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₂	C	58.53	58.53	-	-	+	+
				H	4.20	4.25				
				N	12.42	12.81				

* - = No inhibition
 + = Zone size 6-8 mm
 ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm
 +++ = Zone size greater than 10 mm.

0.5% glucose, 2.5% bactopectone; pH 6.8-7.0) after drying up the solvent. The plates were incubated at 37° for 24 hr and the zones of inhibition around the discs were measured. Bacterial cultures maintained at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, were used.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries in a liquid bath and are uncorrected.

Condensation of I with Aryl Aldehydes (II)

Equimolar amounts of substituted diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides (I) and appropriate aromatic aldehyde were refluxed in 95% ethanol on a water bath for 3-4 hr. The excess of solvent was distilled off under vacuum and the crude products were recrystallised from ethanol. Yields 70-75% (Table 1).

Condensation of I with Aryl ketones (III)

One mole of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide (I) was dissolved in ethanol and to this solution were added two drops of glacial acetic acid and one mole of appropriate aromatic ketone. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. After cooling the crude product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 65-68% (Table 2).

Condensation of I with α -isonitrosopropiophenone (IV)

To an ethanolic solution of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazide (I) was added an equimolar

amount of α -isonitrosopropiophenone⁶ in the presence of a drop of acetic acid. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. Then the mixture was cooled and water was added drop by drop till a turbidity appeared. The reaction mixture was left overnight and the crystals separated were filtered, dried and recrystallised from absolute ethanol. Yield 75-80% (Table 3).

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. Ram Gopal for his keen interest and encouragement. Grateful acknowledgement is made to C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for micro-analysis. Deep sense of gratitude is due to Dr. S. A. Imam for antibacterial activity. One of them (A.K.G.) is indebted to the U.P. State C.S.I.R. for financial assistance.

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